

The plant population, time of *S. rostrata* harvest, and their interaction were not significant. The rate of urea application, however, was significant.

The rice crop responded to urea application. *S. rostrata* green manure gave the same rice yield as did 46 kg N/ha as urea. Applying urea at 46 kg N/ha could

decrease the unfilled grains/panicle, increase the panicle/hill, and increase grain yield (Table 2). ■

Fertilizer management—Inorganic sources

Band placement of urea solution increases N use efficiency in transplanted lowland rice

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Most of the N fertilizer used in rice in Asia is urea. Rice under flooded systems makes poor use of urea because of losses through ammonia volatilization, denitrification, leaching, immobilization, and ammonium fixation. Scientists at IIRI modified a technique where urea solution is placed in bands using a two-row, push-type applicator for transplanted lowland rice. Nitrogen use efficiency (NUE) and rice yield were significantly increased using this technique compared

with point placement of urea supergranules (USG).

We evaluated the IIRI applicator for urea solution (see figure) with broadcast prilled urea (PU), neem-coated urea (NCU), and point placement of USG at Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Aliyar Nagar, Tamil Nadu, during 1992-93, followed by on-farm testing. The experiments were laid out in randomized complete block design with 11 treatments and three replications using varieties IR50 and ADT36.

All growth and yield parameters increased significantly (see table) with band placement of urea solution at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits compared with applying 100 kg N/ha as PU in a conventional 3-way split. The grain yield increase with band placement was 10% more for IR50 and 25% more for ADT36 than that

Urea solution applicator.

with the 3-way PU split. Higher agronomic efficiency and apparent recovery of N were obtained with band placement (see table) of urea solution. At 100 kg N/ha, the optimal growth and yield parameters also occurred with band placement.

Effect of treatments on yield components, yield, and N use efficiency in rice. ARS, Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

Treatment	N rate (kg/ha)	Panicles/m ² (no.)		Yield (t/ha)				N use efficiency			
				Grain		Straw		Agronomic efficiency (kg grain/kg N)		Apparent recovery (%)	
				IR50	ADT36	IR50	ADT36	IR50	ADT36	IR50	ADT36
Control (No N)	0	460	420	3.6	3.8	3.8	4.7	-	-	-	-
BC ^a 50% N as basal + 25% N each at 15 and 35 DAT ^b as PU ^c	100	510	435	4.6	5.4	4.6	5.6	10.3	15.8	18.3	22.8
BP ^d of urea solution at 1/3 N at 15 DAT + 2/3 N at 35 DAT	50	600	603	5.1	6.8	6.1	8.3	30.0	59.1	62.1	95.2
BP of urea solution at 1/3 N at 15 DAT + 2/3 N at 35 DAT	100	615	625	5.2	7.1	6.2	8.4	16.3	32.4	35.3	55.9
Point placement of USG ^e at 7 DAT	100	565	550	4.9	6.6	5.2	7.5	13.5	27.5	25.8	42.9
BC 50% N as basal as NCU ^f + 25% N at 15 DAT as NBU ^g + 25% N at 35 DAT as PU	100	555	495	4.8	6.6	5.0	8.0	12.3	27.3	22.5	40.9
LSD (0.05)		12	29	0.3	0.7	0.3	0.9	(Not analyzed statistically)			

^a BC = broadcasting. ^b DAT = days after transplanting. ^c PU = prilled urea. ^d BP = band placement. ^e USG = urea supergranules. ^f NCU = neem-coated urea. ^g neem-blended urea.

¹⁵N studies showed that conventional application of PU resulted in low recovery and that the major portion of applied N appeared to have been lost (data not shown). The plant and total (plant + soil)

recovery of ¹⁵N improved with band placement of urea solution at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits compared with applying PU.

Band placement of urea solution at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits is an alternate

fertilizer management strategy for reducing N losses, increasing yield, and obtaining higher NUE to achieve about a 6.5 t/ha yield potential. ■

Transformation of N in soil affected by different sources and methods of N application in a flooded rice ecosystem

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We investigated the effect of applying 60 kg N/ha through various sources and methods on rice cultivar IET4094 during 1992-93 rabi (wet) and 1993 kharif (dry) seasons at the university's farm in Kalyani, West Bengal, India.

Soil was a Haplustalf with a pH of 7.9, 0.85% organic C, 26.32 C mol (p⁺)/kg CEC, and 0.993% total N. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Nitrogen was applied according to the schedule in

the table. We applied 13.34 kg P/ha and 24.89 kg K/ha basally across the entire area at final puddling.

Two to three 25-d-old rice seedlings were transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing. Various fractions of N in the soil, including ammonium-N, nitrate-N (using 10% NaCl solution as an extractant in the ratio of 1:4, soil:solution), hydrolyzable N (HL-N) (6 N HCl), and nonhydrolyzable-N (NHL-N) (acid-nonhydrolysate) were measured, as well as N losses through ammonia volatilization (trapping evolved NH₃ in 0.1 N H₂SO₄) and leaching (soil solution collected by a piezometer with a porous cup). Rice yield was also recorded.

Applying (NH₄)₂SO₄ basally maintained a higher concentration of ammonium N in the soil than did most treatments during kharif. Soil NO₃-N values

with prilled urea (PU) as a basal application and PU as a split were similar in both seasons while green manure (GM) + PU resulted in a generally lower soil nitrate N concentration. Use of neem-coated urea applied basally maintained relatively high amounts of both HL-N and NHL-N.

The cumulative N loss through ammonia volatilization in GM + PU was similar to that of PU (split) during both seasons. The N loss through leaching was generally lower with the PU as a split than with the other treatments during both seasons (see table).

We concluded that applying PU as a split and GM + PU are the most efficient fertilization forms of those studied. They resulted in generally higher yields with relatively low N losses to volatilization and leaching. ■

Transformation of N in submerged soil in relation to yield of rice cultivar IET4094^a. West Bengal, India. 1992-93.

Treatment	NH ₄ ⁺ - N (mg/kg)		NO ₃ ⁻ - N (mg/kg)		Hydrolyzable-N (mg/kg)		Nonhydrolyzable-N (mg/kg)	
	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi
Control	2.58 d	2.12 d	0.60 c	0.62 d	595.75 d	634.00 d	140.00 d	120.25 e
Prilled urea (basal)	5.34 a	4.27 b	0.89 a	0.89 a	686.25 bc	703.40 b	150.50 c	157.25 d
Prilled urea (1/2 at transplanting + 1/2 at 30 DAT ^b)	4.29 b	3.26 c	0.82 ab	0.89 a	687.50 bc	691.00 bc	164.75 a	168.75 a
Neem-coated urea	3.86 c	3.85 bc	0.88 a	0.68 cd	701.75 a	738.50 a	160.45 ab	165.75 ab
Sulfur-coated urea	3.68 c	3.77 bc	0.81 ab	0.71 bc	691.30 ab	717.25 b	162.50 a	164.25 abc
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	5.71 a	4.99 a	0.88 a	0.78 b	684.50 bc	700.75 bc	156.50 b	160.30 de
Green manure ^c + prilled urea (1:1)	4.50 b	4.42 ab	0.75 b	0.72 bc	673.25 c	681.75 c	165.25 a	163.40 bc

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT. ^b DAT = days after transplanting. ^c Green manure = *Sesbania rostrata* in kharif and *Anabaena azollae* in rabi.

Effect of substituting sodium for potassium in a lowland double-rice cropping system

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We evaluated the effect of substituting sodium (common salt) for potassium

(muriate of potash) in indica, japonica, and hybrid rices during 1990-91 in three soils with different K-supplying capacities.

Soils (top 0-15 cm) were Yu-yao silty-clay loam (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 6.2, 13.3 g organic C/kg, 1.83 g total N/kg, 19.3 g K/kg, 263 kg available N/ha, 20.50 kg Olsen P/ha, 77 kg exchangeable K/ha, 493 kg nonexchangeable K/ha, and

240.15 kg exchangeable Na/ha; Wen-lin loamy clay (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 5.6, 22.0 g organic C/kg, 270 kg available N/ha, 16.09 kg Olsen P/ha, 219 kg exchangeable K/ha, 614 kg nonexchangeable K/ha, and 319.47 kg exchangeable Na/ha; and Shao-Xing loamy clay (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 5.8, 23.3 g organic C/kg, 719 kg available N/ha, 6.18 kg Olsen P/ha, 137 kg exchangeable K/ha,